

Visha Cikitsa Management in Triple Insect Bite Case

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Abstract

Insect bites are considered as *keeta visha* in *Ayurveda* which includes scorpion, honey bee, spider, ants etc., generally *keeta visha* are *pitta dosha pradhana* but also based on involvement of *doshas* signs and symptoms get manifested. Based on the *lakshana* involvement of *doshas* can be elicited. In *keeta vishas usha cikitsa* is not indicated as it is *pitta pradhana*. But exceptions are there based on *dosha* predominance. Here I'm presenting the three insect bite cases among three two cases are related to unknown insects but it was a sting bite. One case is of honey bee bite. After a bite or sting of insects there was a symptom of swelling, burning pain and itching. Among three cases two were online consultation and one was offline consultation. After consultation treatment was started with one oral medication and one lepa for bite area. Within one or two dosage of medicines symptoms got reduced and patient was completely relieved from all complaints. Line of treatment used here is completely *vishahara cikitsa*, which is also a *pitta hara* along with *vishagna karma*. Within a two dose or within a day all the symptoms reduced and patients were treated successfully.

Key words: insect bites, *keeta visha*, *visha cikitsa*, triple case.

Introduction:

According to *Acharya Charka*, insects are also called *keetas* because they are produced from the waste products like stool and urine of the snakes. According to *Vachaspatya*, it is defined that '*Krimibhyah Sthoole Kshudra jantu Bhede*' i.e., *Keeta* is one of the *Krimi* with macroscopic body¹. *Keetas* as per *Ayurveda* generally originated from waste products of higher animals, dust, wood waste, brick waste etc^{2,3}, based on its origin *dosha* predominant will be there, but most of the *keetas* are *pitta and vata dosha pradhana*⁴. Because of that there will be presentation of reddish discoloration, swelling, local raised in temperature, burning sensation and pain⁵. Most of the time it will be localised symptoms, which gradually turns to systemic in nature. Hence it's very important to treat the cases as early as possible to avoid further complications.

Materials and methods:

Case No: 1

Patient is from telangana consultation is in online flat form, patient contacted me with the complaint of some insect bitten at fore head while walking in the garden, he didn't noticed which insect it was, after few minutes there was swelling over fore head which was disturbing his vision because of swelling, there was bit burning sensation and pain was more comparatively and also swelling of eyes started. Immediately they consulted me, I started with one oral medicine and *lepa* over fore head, gradually pain and swelling reduced by second dose of medicine and by the evening completely reduced.

Case No: 2

Patient came with the complaint of insect bite over left medial above the eye lid while riding bike, patient orally consulted through phone call, at that time there was no swelling but mild itching and pain was there, advised medications patient did not took the medicine, next day morning there was a swelling of eye with pricking pain. On direct consultation of the patient, there was a symptom of swelling of eye, itching, pricking pain and watery discharge. On local application of medication for once, patient relieved from swelling and pain, mild itching with mild discharge was persisting. At the end of the same day almost 90 % of the symptoms reduced and on next day complete relief was seen

Case No: 3

Patient is from KR Nagar consultation is in online flat form, patient contacted me with the complaint of honey bee bite near right eye, where swelling was present which leads to the vision difficulty and pain was there. Patient said no any stings at the bite site so oral medication and external application was advised. After two dose of medicine gradually symptoms reduced by the nest day patient was completely normal.

Case No 1

Case No 2

Case No 3

Details of Given Treatment:

Case Number	Treatment	External Application	Duration
Case No 1	<i>Bilwadi gulika</i> ⁶ 1-1-1-1 stat	<i>Haridra</i> ⁷ <i>tulsi</i> ⁸ <i>lepa</i> - 2days	QID for 1 day BD for 2 days
Case No 2	<i>Bilwadi gulika</i> 1-1-1	<i>Bilwadi Gulika with tulsi swarasa</i>	for 3 days
Case No 3	<i>Bilwadi gulika</i> 1-1-1	<i>Bilwadi Gulika with tulsi swarasa</i>	for 3 days

Discussion:

As per the *Ayurveda* insects are born of semen, faeces, urine, putrefied dead body and eggs⁹ etc., based on *lakshanas doshas* can be identified, apart from the dosha here in all the insects bite sting will be acting as *visha* which is a foreign object to the body, when any foreign object enters to the body our body immune system will be triggered and there will be rush of inflammatory markers, cytokines and histamines in the affected site because of that there will be signs of swelling, redness, itching, burning sensation, pain and local raised temperature. Based on this we can consider *that keeta visha are pitta pradhana tridoshaja* condition. *Bilwadi gulika is Agada*(anti poisonous) indicated in all the insect bites like scorpion, spider etc., snake bites, *garavisha, jwara*, food infectious conditions¹⁰ etc., hence I used *bilwadi gulika* here in all the three cases for both internally and externally and also *bilwadi gulika* acts on *tridoshas*. *Haridra* and *tulsi* are *vishagna, kandughna, sothahara* in action along with *bilwadi gulika haridra and tulsi* are used for external application, also all the combination of medicines used here are easily available. And all the three cases are not of that much severe in presentation only *bilwadi gulika* was sufficient to treat the cases.

Conclusion:

Bilwadi gulika shows its effectiveness in all the insect bite cases and along with the action of *haridra and tulsi* for external application. *Visha cikitsa* management shows its effectiveness and successfully treated in all the three insect bite cases.

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